

Religiosity and Death Anxiety among Muslim Middle-aged Adults in Indonesia

¹Coriena Lathifa Dewi, ^{2,*}Fitri Ayu Kusumaningrum

^{1,2}Indonesian Islamic University,

Psychology Study Program, Indonesian Islamic University,
Sleman, DI Yogyakarta 55584, Indonesia

Abstract - There is a lot of literature said that religiosity is one of the factors that can affect death anxiety. This study aims to determine the relationship between religiosity and death anxiety (DA) experienced by Muslim middle-aged adults. The participants were 104 respondents with an age range between 30 and 59 years. Furthermore, the correlational method was used with religiosity as the independent variable and death anxiety as the dependent. EFA analysis was used to modify and evaluate the items in this study. The DA was measured by The Arabic Scale of Death Anxiety by Abdel-Khalek (2004) while religiosity was measured by the Religiosity Scale for Muslim subjects by Amir (2021). The results showed a negative significant relationship between religiosity and death anxiety with a correlation coefficient of -0.212^* and a significance of 0.015 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates the proposed hypothesis is accepted. The demographic factors were further discussed including employment status, healthy lifestyle, and congenital diseases.

Keywords:- Death anxiety, religiosity, middle-aged adults.

I. INTRODUCTION

Death anxiety (DA) is felt by everyone when they think about events related to impending and unavoidable death. Abdel-Khalek (2004) stated that DA is felt by individuals because it is something that humans have feared since ancient times. According to Abdel-Khalek (2004), aspects of this anxiety are fear of dead people and tombs, which is caused by shadows of the deceased and funerals. There is also fear of postmortem events which occur after death, as well as pain and torment in the grave.

Lehto & Stein (2009) stated that DA is caused by human knowledge about unavoidable death and it is said to be a psychological problem. Cai, et al (2017) interpreted it as a special type of anxiety associated with death, which is felt by middle-aged individuals. Middle age is a period of transition from early adulthood to the next stage which ranges from 30 to 60 years according to Havighurst (Capuzzi & Stauffer, 2016). Individuals in this phase are aware they are getting old, and begin to think more about the rest of their life (Havighurst, 1980). This phase is the peak of social life and career which makes people's schedules not to be balanced with health, leading to the emergence of several diseases that reduce the quality of life (Santrock, 2013). Furthermore, middle-aged individuals experience higher anxiety than early adults (Suhail & Akram, 2002), and 60 respondents showed more DA in the middle-adult phase (Merizka, et al., 2019).

The effects of death anxiety on individuals are related to emotional disorders such as depression, psychosomatic, neuroticism, and others (Feifel & Nagy, 1981). Also, individuals have negative emotions, feelings of worry, insecurity, tension, anxiety, and a sense of death threat or disaster (Abdel-Khalek, 2005). DA makes people feel sad, affects sleep quality, loss of appetite, fear, and irritable (Irawati et al. 2011). The causes of DA include demographics, internal, as well as external factors. The demographic factors are gender, age, and individual employment status (Rasmussen & Johnson, 1994; Chuin & Choo, 2009; Dadfar et al, 2018; McCabe & Daly, 2018; Saleem & Saleem, 2019; Shakil et al., 2021). Meanwhile, the internal factors are ego integrity, healthy lifestyle, health, as well as religious ideology (Feifel & Nagy, 1981; Thorson et al, 1997; Lehto & Stein, 2009; Morris & Tina, 2009; Saleem et al, 2015; Ardias & Purwari, 2019; Wang & Geng, 2019; Ghayas & Batool, 2021). The external factors are individual experiences regarding the death of someone around them, and how families discuss the phenomenon (Ens & Bond, 2007; Lehto & Stein, 2009; Yuksel et al, 2017; Yin et al, 2020).

Religiosity is how people believe in religion, practice, live, behave, and have a relationship with their creator. Allport & Ross (1967) defined religiosity as an intrinsic aspect of how an individual believes in religion and an extrinsic aspect of how it is practiced. Furthermore, it is a measure of the belief in God along with religious teachings, how worship is practiced, as well as connections (Amir, 2021). These aspects are religious beliefs, practices, and experiences (Amir, 2021). All three can be associated with death anxiety as a theoretical basis in this study.

The first aspect is religious belief, where people believe that Allah (SWT) is God Almighty, the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) as the bearer of revelation, and the Qur'an as the holy book of Islam (Amir, 2021). Religious belief is influential and related to DA, where a Muslim believes in life after death, hence they have lower anxiety. This is in accordance with Suhail & Akram (2002) where Muslim respondents have strong beliefs in life after death and show a strong commitment to practicing Islam. Furthermore, it was added that belief and dedication to religious teachings provide a buffer for the frightening dimension of death.

The second aspect is religious practice, which is the extent to which a person follows the religious teachings, such as obligatory and sunnah worship, studies, da'wah, and others (Amir, 2021). The act of worship gives individuals the hope of surviving life after death. Furthermore, positive activities where a lot of time is spent seeking information and

knowledge about Islam helps to prevent negative thought. Pargament, et al (2004) stated that religiosity affects coping with stress through prayer, support, forgiveness, and relearning about the religion. One of the negative thoughts that can be prevented or buffered is death anxiety. This is in accordance with Saleem & Saleem (2019) on 200 participants as members of Islamic studies, where they often carry out joint religious practices such as following da'wah. The results showed the higher the religiosity of an individual, the lower the death anxiety.

The third aspect is religious experience, which includes appreciation in carrying out practices, hence positive relationships and meaningful personal experiences are formed (Amir, 2021). Religious experience for a Muslim can also be obtained from all the graces given by Allah (SWT) in life. According to Park, et al (2009), it helps to overcome stress by focusing on positive things, hence it is psychologically beneficial. Saroglou (2014) stated that religion soothes the fear of death based on the individual's achievements and contributions. The appreciation involved in religiosity reduces the accessibility of individual death thoughts.

Downey's (1984) study titled Relationship of Religiosity to Death Anxiety of Middle-Aged male subjects between 40-59 years showed a value of 1.70. This indicated no correlation between DA and religiosity. This is similar to Muthoharoh & Andriani (2014) which showed a p-value of 0.425, indicating no relationship between religiosity and middle-aged adults' death anxiety.

However, there are differences in the results of previous studies on the significance value, some of which have a negative correlation. Archentari & Siswati's (2014) studied The Relationship between Religiosity and Anxiety Against Death in Middle-aged Adults at PT Tiga Serangkai Group employees between 35-60 years. The results showed a correlation between religiosity and death anxiety with a significance of 0.030 in a negative direction. The same results were also presented by Merizka, et al (2019), where the correlation number was 0.004 significant in a negative direction. Furthermore, Saleem & Saleem (2019) showed a significant correlation of 0.01 in the negative direction.

From the review of the journals described above, some research gaps can be used as reasons to re-examine the relationship between religiosity and death anxiety. This study used the Arabic Scale of Death Anxiety (ASDA) developed by Abdel-Khalek (2004) which focused on Muslim subjects. Furthermore, the religiosity measuring instrument used was the Religiosity Scale for Muslim subjects developed by Amir (2021). It is focused on Muslims in Indonesia and is the latest tool developed. Although all correlation results were in a negative direction, significant and different results were found in the previously described journals. Several studies proved a significant negative correlation between religiosity and death anxiety (Archentari & Siswati, 2014; Merizka et al, 2019; Saleem & Saleem, 2019), and others showed no correlation between the two variables (Downey, 1984; Muthoharoh & Andriani, 2014). Therefore, the differences in

these results can be used as a gap to re-examine the two variables.

II. METHOD

This study used a correlational method with religiosity as the independent variable and death anxiety as the dependent. Furthermore, a quantitative approach was used with a non-experimental design, and the respondents were selected using the purposive sampling technique. The criteria include Muslim middle-aged adults between 30-60 years according to Havighurst's theory of development.

The measuring instrument for death anxiety was used to obtain data on the Arab Scale of Death Anxiety (ASDA) by Abdel-Khalek (2004) which has a total of 20 items. The alternative answers provided on this scale use a 5-point intensity scale with a score of 1 for "no" answer choice and 5 for "very much". Meanwhile, the instrument for measuring the religiosity variable used the Religiosity Scale for Muslim subjects developed by Amir (2021) with a total of 13 items. The alternative answer choices provided are four, namely 4 points for "very confident/important/often" and 1 for "don't believe/not important/never". The psychometric quality of the questionnaire needs to be improved so that it is necessary to test the validity by using EFA (Exploratory Factor Analysis).

After the measuring instrument went through an exploratory factor analysis measurement process, there we have the final fit items tested for hypotheses. The fit items for ASDA are item number 2,5,8,9,10,11,15,16,17,19 and the fit items for Religiosity Scale for Muslim subjects are item number 5,6,7,8,12. The exploratory factor analysis was conducted using JASP with the provisions of 0.4 on loading factors.

The procedure began by distributing questionnaires to respondents according to the characteristics of the two measuring instruments that have been selected via the google form link. At the beginning of the form, there is a transparent explanation of the aims and objectives of the study, as well as an agreement column to maintain the research code of ethics. The hypothesis proposed is that there is a negative relationship between religiosity and death anxiety. It was assumed that the higher the religiosity level, the lower the death anxiety.

III. RESULTS

The assumption test was carried out on the obtained data, namely the normality and linearity tests using SPSS for Mac OS software.

A. Normality Test

Variable	P	Conclusion
Religiosity	0.000	Not normal
Death Anxiety	0.200	Normal

Table 1

The normality test results on the religiosity variable were not normally distributed because the significance value

was 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). On the other hand, the death anxiety variable was normally distributed with a significance value of 0.200 ($p > 0.05$).

B. Linearity Test

Variable	Linearity	F	P
Religiosity and Death Anxiety	Linearity	3.605	0.053
	Deviation from Linearity	0.213	0.505

Table 2

The linearity test showed the relationship between religiosity and death anxiety has a significance value of 0.053 ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that the relationship between the two variables is not linear. Furthermore, the variables have a significant value of deviation from linearity of 0.505

D. Intercorrelation Test

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Death Anxiety	1	.887**	.789**	.712**	-.212*	-.212*
2. Fear of lethal disease and postmortem events	.887**	1	.503**	.438**	-.173	-.173
3. Fear of tombs	.789**	.503**	1	.595**	-.168	-.168
4. Fear of dead people	.712**	.438**	.595**	1	-.233*	-.233*
5. Religiosity	-.212*	-.173	-.168	-.233*	1	1.000*
6. Belief and religious practice	-.212*	-.173	-.168	-.233*	1.000*	1

Table 4

Description:

* $p < .05$ (there is a significant correlation) , ** $p < .01$ (there is a significant correlation)

The coefficient value in red indicates the absence of a correlation.

E. Correlation Test Based on Gender

Gender	r	r ²	p
Female	-0.105	0.011	0.229
Male	-0.252*	0.063	0.036

Table 5

Based on Table 5, the correlation test by genders showed a significance value of 0.229

($p > 0.05$) in women and 0.036 ($p < 0.05$) in men. This value implies there is a negative correlation between religiosity and DA for male, but no correlation with the female.

F. Test for the Difference between Death Anxiety and Gender

Category	Death Anxiety	
	Sig.	Mean Rank
Female	0.018	59.51
Male		45.49

Table 6

Based on Table 6, the results of the difference test between death anxiety in female and male categories showed a significance value of 0.018 ($p < 0.05$). This shows

($p > 0.05$), which indicates that their relationship does not deviate from the linear line.

C. Hypothesis Testing

Variable	r	r ²	p	Conclusion
Religiosity and Death Anxiety	-0.212*	0.044	0.015	Significant

Table 3

The results of the one-tailed Spearman Rho correlation hypothesis test between religiosity and death anxiety showed a significance value of 0.015 ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, the proposed trending hypothesis is accepted.

Apart from testing the correlation between religiosity and death anxiety, an inter correlation test was conducted between each aspect and the variables. The following are the intercorrelation test results:

a difference between females' and males' death anxiety, where the former have higher DA than the latter.

G. Correlation Test Based on Congenital Disease

Congenital Disease	r	r ²	p
Presence	-0.147	0.021	0.300
Absence	-0.212*	0.044	0.023

Table 7

According to Table 7, the correlation test results based on the presence of congenital diseases showed a significance value of 0.300 ($p > 0.05$) in respondents who had congenital diseases and 0.023 ($p < 0.05$) in those who do not. This value suggests there is a negative correlation between religiosity and death anxiety for those who do not have congenital diseases, but no correlation for those who have a congenital disease.

H. Differential Test of Death Anxiety with Congenital Disease

Category	Death Anxiety	
	Sig.	Mean Rank
Have congenital disease	0.426	58.23
Do not have congenital disease		51.53

Table 8

Based on Table 8, the difference test of death anxiety with respondents who have and do not have a congenital disease showed a significance value of 0.426 ($p > 0.05$). This indicates no difference in DA between those with congenital disease and those without.

I. Correlation Test Based on Occupational Status

Occupational status	r	r ²	p
Workers (Employees and Entrepreneurs)	-0.188	0.035	0.084
Unemployment	-0.251*	0.063	0.041

Table 9

Based on Table 9, the correlation test showed a significance value of 0.084 ($p > 0.05$) for respondents who work and 0.041 ($p < 0.05$) for those who do not. This denotes no correlation between religiosity and DA for employed respondents. On the other hand, there is a negative correlation for unemployed ones.

J. Differential Test of Death Anxiety with Occupational Status

Category	Death anxiety	
	Sig.	Mean Rank
Workers (Employees and Entrepreneurs)	0.401	54.85
Unemployment		49.87

Table 10

Based on Table 10, the different tests of death anxiety and occupational status showed a significance value of 0.401 ($p > 0.05$). This implies no significant difference in DA between employed and unemployed respondents.

K. Correlation Test Based on Healthy Lifestyle

Healthy Lifestyle	r	r ²	p
Have a healthy lifestyle	-0.175	0.030	0.065
Not having a healthy lifestyle	-0.177	0.031	0.277

Table 11

Based on Table 11, the correlation test showed a significance value of 0.065 ($p > 0.05$) for respondents with a healthy lifestyle and 0.277 for those without. This signifies no correlation between religiosity and DA for those who have or do not have a healthy lifestyle.

L. Differential Test of Death Anxiety with a Healthy Lifestyle

Category	Death anxiety	
	Sig.	Mean Rank
Have a healthy lifestyle	0.077	49.33
Not having a healthy lifestyle		61.11

Table 12

Based on Table 12, the difference test above showed a significance value of 0.077 ($p > 0.05$) for respondents who have and who do not have a healthy lifestyle. This no significant difference between the two categories of respondents.

IV. DISCUSSION

The data obtained consisted of 104 middle-aged adult respondents between 30-59 years. The analysis showed there is a negative correlation between the two variables, with a value of $r = -0.212^*$ and a significance of 0.015 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates a significant relationship between religiosity and death anxiety. Therefore, it can be stated that the hypothesis is accepted. This finding is in accordance with Fakhurrozi (2008), Wen (2010), Archentari & Siswati (2014), Merizka, et al (2014), and Saleem & Saleem (2019). A significant negative correlation between religiosity and DA shows that the higher individual's religiosity, the lower DA and vice versa.

Individuals with high religious appreciation and focus on pursuing the afterlife will view death as a means to meet Allah SWT, so they have lower death anxiety (Fakhurrozi, 2008). Individuals who often attend and participate in religious activities can reduce negative thoughts, so they can better in controlling anxiety and fear of death (Wen, 2010). Archentari & Siswati (2014) explain that religiosity plays a role in reducing death anxiety because individuals find the meaning of death for life and are more ready to accept the fate of death so that worry and fear of death can be overcome. The importance of religiosity as a factor influencing death anxiety is explained by Merizka, et al (2019), where the positive effect of an individual's behavior and belief in his religion increases the meaning of life. Practicing good worship and doing useful activities in religion can provide encouragement and hope to be positive.

Merizka, et al (2019) added that religiosity makes individuals accept the fate of death more readily, so that the worries and anxieties caused by the thought of the death process can be overcome through religious teachings and practices. For a Muslim, death is the return of the soul to Allah SWT, where death is unavoidable and believing in the goodness and power of Allah SWT helps overcome death anxiety (Saleem & Saleem, 2019). Attitudes in the face of death can be expressed consciously and unconsciously by individual beliefs. The existence of a significant correlation in this study does not support the results of research conducted by Downey (1984), Rasmussen & Johnson (1994), Azaiza (2010), Muthoharoh & Andriani (2014), and Marin (2019). The results of their research showed that there was no relationship between religiosity and death anxiety.

In the DA context, Islam has a concept of anxiety, namely *khauf* and *raja'*. Imam al-Ghazali, Yusuf (2020) defined *khauf* as a disease that attacks and burns the heart, hence it feels hot, dirty, and black. The defilements in the heart can give rise to bad occurrences, such as death. Meanwhile, *raja'* is a feeling of joy which will come to an

individual. A Muslim is expected to have a balance between the *khauf* and *raja'* in order to avoid problems by believing that Allah SWT will show mercy and compassion with the attitude of the *raja'*, therefore, there is no fear of death.

The measuring tool for death anxiety is less maladaptive and more normative. The instrument used is also not sufficient to detect the attitude of a Muslim. Hence, the religiosity variable is suggested to be mediated through the *raja'* theory in order to reduce anxiety. This shows the importance of the mediator to control the two variables. The age theory used needs to be considered because the author used Havighurst's theory, where the age range of middle-aged adults is 30-60 years. However, in Islam, the age at which a Muslim finds the peak of wisdom and enters the middle-aged adult phase starts from 40 years. At this age, it is recommended to renew repentance, increase worship, and draw closer to Allah SWT.

The results showed a negative significant relationship between religiosity and DA among men. However, another result showed that women have higher death anxiety. This is in line with Rasmussen & Johnson (1994), Tang, et al (2002), Yuksel, et al (2016), and Saleem & Saleem (2019). According to Abdel-Khalek (2005), this is due to a social construct in which men are not allowed to cry, hence they find it difficult to express their feelings compared to women. Also, Merizka, et al (2019) stated that the difference in the mindset of men and women could be a different factor in dealing with death anxiety.

Based on employment status, there is a significant negative relationship between religiosity and DA of unemployed respondents. Work is one of the factors that protect an individual in the event of anxiety. According to McCabe & Daly (2018), unemployed people tend to have higher DA. Psychological distress associated with death anxiety is more significant for unemployed people than for those who are employed (Shakil et al, 2021). Occupation is a factor that restrains anxiety associated with death thought, therefore it has significance for moderating and inhibiting DA.

Another result showed a negative significant relationship between religiosity and DA among respondents who don't have congenital diseases. According to Santrock (2013), middle-aged adults begin to experience a decline in their health quality. Santrock (2013) stated that health problems are among the reasons why middle-aged adults think about their life. Physical health and congenital diseases are one of the main causes of death anxiety. This is because when health is threatened by illness, there are thoughts of future death anxiety (Lehto & Stein, 2009; Saleem et al, 2015).

Furthermore, the analysis was also carried out on the category of respondents' healthy lifestyle. Wang & Geng (2019) stated that those with a healthy lifestyle have better psychological health. Yin, et al (2020) stated that physical condition is one of the factors that affect DA. According to Zhang (in Yin et al, 2020), varying physical conditions

produce significant differences in dealing with death anxiety. Additionally, physical condition and health are important factors in how individuals think about impending death.

V. CONCLUSION

There is a negative relationship between religiosity and death anxiety, therefore, the hypothesis in this study is accepted. Also, the DA in women is higher than in men, and there is a significant negative correlation between religiosity and death anxiety in men, respondents who don't have congenital diseases and unemployed respondents.

This study has several limitations, hence it is recommended that further research should use a more maladaptive instrument to measure and detect death anxiety. The religiosity scale in this study did not detect *raja'*, therefore it is better to be mediated with the concept to reduce DA. The theory of determining the age of respondents needs to be considered, where the middle age range should start from 40-60 years. More respondents are also needed to support the hypothesis.

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AUTHORS BIOGRAPHY

Annisa Anin Sari a student majoring in psychology at the Islamic University of Indonesia, is currently in her 8th semester. She had an internship at the Psychology Bureau of Kinderhutte, Tangerang Indonesia in the position of assistant psychologist. Her research team won 1st place in the experimental research methodology group competition. On campus, she was a practicum assistant for children and youth. She and her friends have also succeeded in publishing a community service journal. She is interested in developmental psychology which discusses the growth and development of children to the elderly.

Fitri Ayu Kusumaningrum become a teaching staff in the psychology department Universitas Islam Indonesia, with a focus on human development psychology, especially children, adolescents, and adults. Research development and community service are directed at the topic of interest